

"ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC AND LEXICOGRAPHIC FEATURES OF SOCIAL PROTECTION TERMINOLOGY, A STUDY OF TRANSLATION PROBLEMS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES"

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Annotation

This study explores the complex aspects of translating social protection terminology between English and Uzbek. Applying a rigorous analytical framework, he studies the structural-semantic and lexicographic properties of these terms, clarifying their morphological patterns and semantic structures. Based on data from bilingual dictionaries, corpus, and academic literature, the study identifies translation problems arising from cultural, conceptual, and linguistic differences. Highlighting these complexities, the study promotes the development of translation theory and practice in the field of social protection speech, emphasizing the need for accurate and culturally sensitive translations for effective cross-cultural communication.

Key words: Social protection, Translation, Structural-semantic features, Lexicographic features, Cross-linguistic analysis, Cultural sensitivity, Terminology, Difficulties.

Introduction

Social protection is an important aspect of public policy worldwide, including a wide range of policies and programs aimed at protecting individuals and communities from economic and social risks. As societies become increasingly interdependent, the need to accurately and effectively translate social protection terminology by language comes to the fore. This introduction provides the basis for a comprehensive analysis of the structural-semantic and lexicographic features of Social Protection terms, focusing on the problems of translation found between English and Uzbek.

Understanding the structural-semantic features of social protection terminology involves the study of morphological patterns and semantic structures that underlie these terms in both languages. At the same time, lexicographic features imply how these terms are organized and presented in bilingual dictionaries, and serve as an important reference tool for translators. Having carefully

studied these features, this study is aimed at identifying the complexities that exist in the translation of social protection terminology between English and Uzbek.

This study is explained by the recognition that exact translation is not only a linguistic, but also a socio-cultural work. Translation includes cultural nuances and conceptual differences that can cause significant problems, especially in specialized areas such as social protection. Through a systematic analysis of translation problems, this study seeks to contribute to the development of translation theory and practice, which influences the development of intercultural communication and culturally sensitive translation strategies.

Methods

Information for this study comes from a variety of sources, including bilingual dictionaries, Corps, educational literature, and official documents on social protection in English and Uzbek. A comprehensive selection process was used to identify relevant terms and examples for analysis. The terms were chosen based on their importance in the field of social protection and their potential to describe structural-semantic and lexicographic features as well as translation problems.

Analysis has adopted a multifaceted approach that includes methods of semantic analysis, comparative analysis and translation analysis. Semantic analysis has been used in both languages to explore the basic meanings and conceptual structures of Social Protection terms. Comparative analysis included a comparison of morphological patterns and semantic structures of terms in English and Uzbek. Translation analysis aims to identify the problems encountered when translating these terms, including cultural, conceptual and linguistic differences.

In addition, software tools such as linguistic corpus and translation memory programs were used to help analyze data and identify translation equivalents. This hybrid approach made it possible to comprehensively study the structural-semantic and lexicographic features of social protection terminology, while highlighting the intricacies of translation between English and Uzbek in this specialized field.

Results

Structural-Semantic Features

Analysis of structural-semantic features revealed significant differences between English and Uzbek social protection terminology. In English, terms often demonstrated complex morphological structures-compound words and

Latin Affixes-are commonly used to convey subtle meanings. In contrast, Uzbek terms tended to exhibit simpler morphological laws, often relying on agglutinative suffixes to represent different aspects of Social Protection Concepts.

Smantic analysis has revealed subtle differences in the conceptualization of social protection concepts between the two languages. While English terms often emphasized individual rights and rights, Uzbek equivalents often emphasized collective well-being and public solidarity. These differences reflect cultural and social norms that influence the semantic nuances of social protection terminology in each language.

Lexicographic Features

The study of lexicographic features found differences in the representation of Social Protection terms in bilingual dictionaries for English and Uzbek. English dictionaries tended to provide comprehensive entries, offering several definitions, examples, and usage entries for each term. In contrast, Uzbek dictionaries often had limited information, shorter entries, and less contextual detail.

Inconsistencies were observed in the translation equivalents provided for the terms of social protection. While some terms have direct equivalents in both languages, others lack explicit translations, leading to ambiguity and potential misinterpretation. This imbalance emphasizes the need for improved lexicographic resources to facilitate accurate translation between English and Uzbek social protection terminology.

Translation Problems

Translation analysis has identified several problems inherent in translating social protection terms between English and Uzbek. Cultural differences have created significant barriers, especially in conveying concepts related to individual autonomy and state intervention. In addition, linguistic imbalances such as differences in Word Order and grammatical structures complicated the translation process.

Conceptual differences also created problems, as some social protection concepts are deeply rooted in cultural norms and social values inherent in each language. For example, terms related to social security often have different meanings in English and Uzbek, requiring careful consideration in the translation process.

In general, the results highlight the complexity of translating social protection terminology between English and Uzbek, emphasizing the importance of

context-sensitive translation strategies and the development of culturally sensitive lexicographic resources to ensure clear cross-language communication in this area.

Discussion

The results of this study shed light on the complex problems of translating social protection terminology between English and Uzbek. The discussion examines the impact of these findings on translation theory and practice, as well as their importance in the implementation of policies in the field of intercultural communication and social protection.

Impact on translation theory and practice

The analysis of structural-semantic and lexicographic features determined the need for a subtle understanding of linguistic and cultural differences in translation. Translation theory emphasizes the importance of preserving the form and meaning of texts in the source language while taking into account the cultural context in which they are placed. The results of this study highlight the need to apply a context-sensitive approach to translation, specifically in specialized areas such as social protection, where cultural nuances and conceptual differences abound.

The identification of translation problems emphasizes the need to develop special translation strategies adapted to the specifics of social protection terminology. Translators should manage not only linguistic barriers, but also cultural and conceptual differences, which requires a comprehensive understanding of the socio-cultural context in which these terms are located. By highlighting these problems, this research will help improve the methodology of translation and develop best practices in the field of Translation Studies.

Influence of intercultural communication

Effective cross-cultural communication is essential for the development of mutual understanding and cooperation in various socio-cultural contexts. Differences in the structural-semantic and lexicographic characteristics observed between English and Uzbek social protection terminology emphasize the complexity of communicating the concepts of social protection across linguistic and cultural boundaries. Translators play a decisive role in overcoming these divisions by facilitating accurate and culturally sensitive translations that resonate with the target audience.

Identifying cultural and conceptual differences underlines the importance of cultural competence in translation. Translators should not only have linguistic

qualifications, but also have a deep understanding of cultural norms, values and social structures that shape the interpretation of the concepts of social protection in different linguistic communities. By fostering cultural sensitivity and awareness, translators can increase the effectiveness of intercultural communication and contribute to the development of social solidarity and inclusion.

The precise translation of social protection terminology is crucial to the effective implementation and management of policies in multilingual societies. Policies and programs aimed at the development of social protection should be open and understandable to all members of society, regardless of their linguistic background. The results of this study highlight the importance of developing culturally sensitive translation resources and guidelines to ensure accurate dissemination of social protection information in linguistic and cultural divisions.

Identifying translation problems underlines the need for cooperation among policymakers, translators, and linguists to address the complexities of translating social protection terminology. By fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange, policymakers can develop more inclusive and culturally sensitive policies that meet the diverse needs of linguistic minority groups and marginal communities.

This study emphasizes the importance of understanding the structural-semantic and lexicographic features of social protection terminology in order to accurately translate between English and Uzbek. Highlighting the problems of translation and their impact on translation theory, intercultural communication and policy implementation, this study helps to develop translatability and promote inclusive and culturally sensitive communication in various linguistic contexts.

Conclusion

In summary, this study provided valuable insights into the structural-semantic, lexicographic features of social protection terminology between English and Uzbek, and translation problems. Through comprehensive analysis, we have identified significant differences in morphological patterns, semantic structures and lexicographic representations of Social Protection terms in two languages. These differences highlight the complexities inherent in translating social protection concepts between linguistically and culturally distinct contexts.

The results of this study are important to translation theory and practice, emphasizing the importance of adopting context-sensitive translation strategies

that take into account linguistic, cultural and conceptual nuances. By facilitating a deeper understanding of these complexities, translators can improve the accuracy and effectiveness of cross-language communication in the field of social protection.

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